

ANALYTICAL SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENT OF TRANSVERSE CRACKING IN MULTIDIRECTIONAL REINFORCED SYMMETRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Satoshi Abe, Kazuro Kageyama ¹, and Isao Kimpara ²

¹ the University of Tokyo, ² Kanazawa Institute of Technology

SUMMARY: Composite materials have complex damage behavior because of their heterogeneous and anisotropic features. In the present paper, damages of composite materials are classified to three modes, transverse lamina crack, delamination, and fiber breakage. In early damage state, transverse lamina cracks grow stably. The tolerable stress is improved when stable damage growth is permitted. It is assumed that damage initiates and propagates when both criteria are satisfied. One is energy criterion. It is assumed that the crack extension occurs when the energy available for crack growth is sufficient to overcome the resistance of material on energy criterion. The other is stress criterion. It is assumed that the crack extension occurs when the stress reaches at the critical value on stress criterion. Experiment was done to verify the validity of the calculation.

KEYWORDS: Transverse Crack, Delamination, Energy Criterion, Stress Criterion

2. INTRODUCTION

The damage accumulative modes are shown in Fig.1.1. When the composite materials are subjected to a mechanical and a non-mechanical load, transverse lamina cracks initiate and extend, followed by delamination growth. Finally, fiber breakage results in catastrophic fracture of the laminates. In order to estimate initial state of damage processes of composite laminates, behavior of transverse lamina cracking should be studied.

Fig. 2.1 Damage Modes of A Composite Laminate

When no damage is tolerated in structural design, the design strength is limited to onset of transverse lamina cracks. When some extent damage is tolerated, the design strength is improved. The concept of the allowable damage growth makes design strength improved.

It is assumed that damage initiates and propagates when both criteria are satisfied. One is energy criterion. It is assumed that the crack extension occurs when the energy available for crack growth is sufficient to overcome the resistance of material on energy criterion. Failure stress based on energy criterion is in inverse proportion to a square root of the thickness of ply group because of the reason stated in the next chapter. The other is stress criterion. It is assumed that the crack extension occurs when the stress reaches at the critical value on stress criterion. When ply group thickness is thin, stress criterion is satisfied former at point A', and

combined failure criterion is given by energy criterion. Materials fail at point A where energy criterion is satisfied. When ply group thickness is thick, energy criterion is satisfied former at point C', and combined failure criterion is given by stress criterion. Materials fail at point C where stress criterion is satisfied. Combined failure failure criterion exchanges at point B where ply group thickness is the critical thickness, b_c .

Fig. 2.2 Damage Initiation and Growth Criteria

2. DAMAGE PREDICTION THEORY

2.1. Modeling of Laminates

The multidirectional symmetric n layer laminate $[\dots]_s$ is divided into $n-1$ units, U_{n-1}, \dots, U_1 , at the center of each layer as shown in Fig.2.1. The laminate is expressed as a combination of the units.

Fig. 2.1 Division into Units of A Multidirectional Symmetric Laminate

The symmetric laminate unit can be dealt with as the $[\dots]_s$ laminate unit by coordinate transformation. We consider stiffness reduction of the laminate unit with cracks in 90° ply as shown in Fig.2.2.

Fig. 2.2 The Symmetric Area near Transverse Cracks

2.2. Stiffness Reduction of the Symmetric Laminate Unit with Transverse Cracks

The 90° ply is divided into $M \times N$ elements in the z - and y - directions, respectively. The 90° ply is divided into N elements in the y direction, as shown in Fig.2.3. Tensile stresses (m,n) and shear stresses (m,n) are defined at boundaries of the divided elements. These stresses are calculated from equilibrium conditions of stresses, compatibility of strains, and boundary conditions. When the crack density is $c(=1/2L:2L$ is the distance of cracks), and the average tensile stress σ_0 is applied, tensile stresses components (m,n) and shear stresses components (m,n) are obtained. The average tensile stress of the 90° ply σ_{av} is obtained from the tensile stresses of 90° ply $(0,n)$. The average strain of the unit ϵ_{av} is obtained from σ_{av} because the tensile stiffness of the 90° ply does not change by cracks of the 90° ply. The stiffness of the unit is obtained by σ_0 / ϵ_{av} .

Fig. 2.3 Tensile Stiffness Reduction by Cracks

Shear stiffness reduction is calculated by the same way as the aforesaid tensile stiffness reduction as shown in Fig.2.4. The symmetric laminate unit is divided same as the case of tensile stiffness problem. When the shear stress τ_{xy0} is applied, the shear stiffness of the unit is obtained.

Fig. 2.4 Shear Stiffness Reduction by Cracks

2.3. Damage Prediction on Energy Criterion

Matrix cracking failure under mixed mode is predicted when following energy criterion¹⁾²⁾ is satisfied

$$\left(\frac{G}{G_c}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G}{G_c}\right)^\alpha = 1 \quad (2.1)$$

where G and G are the energy release rate of mode I and II, respectively, and G_c and G_c are the fracture toughness of mode I and II, respectively. Cracks initiate and propagate when the total energy release rate $G(=G_I + G_{II})$ reaches mixed mode fracture toughness G_c as follows.

$$G = G_c \quad (2.2)$$

When the mixed mode ratio, M_G , is defined as G_{II}/G_I , the mixed mode fracture toughness is obtained from Eqn.2.1 as follows;

$$G_c = (1 + M_G) \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{G_c}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{M_G}{G_c}\right)^\alpha \right\}^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (2.3)$$

When increment of crack density, $dc^{(1)}$ is given, the energy release rates are expressed as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_I &= -\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2b_1} \varepsilon_y'^2 \frac{dS'_{22}}{dc^{(1)}} - \frac{b_1 + b_2}{2b_1} \gamma_{xy}'^2 \frac{dS'_{66}}{dc^{(1)}} \\ G_{II} &= -\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2b_1} \varepsilon_y'^2 \frac{dS'_{22}}{dc^{(1)}} \\ G_{III} &= -\frac{b_1 + b_2}{2b_1} \gamma_{xy}'^2 \frac{dS'_{66}}{dc^{(1)}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

Critical strains are obtained at each ply. Crack is predicted to initiate or propagate in the ply that gives the smallest critical strain.

2.4. Damage Prediction on Stress Criterion

Matrix cracking failure under combined loads is predicted when the following stress criterion³⁾ is satisfied

$$\left(\frac{f_\sigma \sigma_T}{\sigma_{Tc}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{f_\tau \tau_{LT}}{\tau_{LTc}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (2.4)$$

where σ_T and τ_{LT} are the average ply transverse and shear stresses, respectively, and σ_{Tc} and τ_{LTc} are the effective transverse tensile strength and shear strength of the ply under consideration, respectively. And f_σ and f_τ are the ratios of maximum stresses and average stresses in tensile and shear components. Crack is predicted to initiate or propagate in the ply that gives the smallest critical stress.

2.5. Thermal Residual Stress

Thermal residual stresses $\sigma_R^{(k)}$ occur in each layer because of the difference of thermal expansion coefficients in the longitudinal and transverse direction, respectively, as follow;

$$\sigma_R^{(k)} = \mathbf{S}^{(k)} \left\{ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(c)}(T) - \mathbf{R}_\varepsilon(\theta_k) \boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 (T - T_0) \right\} = \mathbf{S}^{(k)} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_R^{(k)} \quad (2.5)$$

Where $\mathbf{S}^{(k)}$ is stiffness matrix of k ply. \mathbf{R}_ε is a strain transformation matrix. $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0$ is a thermal expansion coefficient vector. When there is thermal stress, the origin of the stress-strain curve shifts from O to O' as shown in Fig.2.5. The critical strain and stress are measured from the new origin O'.

Fig. 2.5 Thermal Residual Stress

3. EXPERIMENT

3.1. Specimens

TR340H150; the carbon/epoxy pre-prig sheet of Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. is served to experiment. Material properties of the CFRP are shown in Table.3.1. The nominal ply thickness is 0.15mm. Cross-ply and quasi-isotropic were prepared with stacking sequences, as shown in Table.3.2.

Table. 3.1 Material Properties of the CFRP

Stiffness		For Residual Stress		For Energy Criterion		For Stress Criterion	
E_L	115GPa	L	$-7.5 \cdot 10^{-7}/K$	G_c	197J/m ²	L_c	1924MPa
E_T	8GPa	T	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-5}/K$	G_c	982J/m ²	T_c	82MPa
G_{LT}	3.5GPa	T_0	120		1	LT_c	110MPa
G_{TZ}	2.5GPa	T_1	20				
LT	0.34						

Table. 3.2 Stacking Sequence of Laminate

Cross-Ply	Quasi-Isotropic
$[0_1/90_1/0_1]_T$	$[45_1/-45_1/0_1/90_1]_s$
$[0_1/90_1]_s$	$[45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2]_s$
$[0_2/90_2]_s$	$[45_1/0_1/-45_1/90_1]_s$
$[0_4/90_4]_s$	

Fig. 3.1 Size of Specimen and Attached Objects

Size of specimen is 20mm × 300mm as shown in Fig.3.1. Edge of specimen was polished for edge observation. Sandpaper was attached on gripping surfaces as shown in Fig.3.1 to prevent from slipping. An axial extensometer with a gage length of 100mm was mounted in the center of specimen. A.E. sensors were mounted out of gage length.

3.2. Method of Experiment

Tension tests of the specimens were performed using the Shimadzu Autograph test machine in the stroke control mode at a loading rate of 0.5mm/min. When initial A.E. wave was detected, crosshead movement was stopped and reversed a little, and cracks were counted by the way of edge observation. This was repeated while strain was increased 1000 or 2000 μ until the specimen breaks.

4. Comparison of Results between Calculation and Experiment

4.1. Cross-Ply Laminates

Fig.4.1 through 4.4 demonstrate the effect of varying 90 ° ply group thickness on matrix cracking in cross-ply laminates. In graphs, \bullet indicates the onset of A.E.

Fig. 4.1 Stress-Strain and 90 ° Ply's Crack Density of $[0_1/90_1/0_1]_T$

Fig.4.1 shows results of $[0_1/90_1/0_1]_T$. The 90 ° ply group thickness is in the region of point A in Fig.1.2. Ply group thickness is so thin that stress criterion is satisfied former, and combined failure criterion becomes energy criterion. Experimental value is close to calculated value on energy criterion.

Fig. 4.2 Stress-Strain and 90 ° Ply Group's Crack Density of $[0_1/90_1]_s$

Fig.4.2 shows results of $[0_1/90_1]_s$. The 90° ply group thickness is in the region of point A in Fig.1.2. Ply group thickness is so thin that stress criterion is satisfied former, and combined failure criterion becomes energy criterion. Experimental value is close to calculated value on energy criterion.

Fig. 4.3 Stress-Strain and 90° Ply Group's Crack Density of $[0_2/90_2]_s$

Fig.4.3 shows results of $[0_2/90_2]_s$. The 90° ply group thickness is in the region of point C in Fig.1.2. Ply group thickness is so thick that energy criterion is satisfied former, and combined failure criterion becomes stress criterion. Experimental value is close to calculated value on stress criterion.

Fig. 4.4 Stress-Strain and 90° Ply Group's Crack Density of $[0_4/90_4]_s$

Fig.4.4 shows results of $[0_4/90_4]_s$. The 90° ply group thickness is in the region of point C in Fig.1.2. Ply group thickness is so thick that energy criterion is satisfied former, and combined failure criterion becomes stress criterion. Experimental value is close to calculated value on stress criterion.

The change of combined failure criteria from energy criterion to stress criterion is well explained by the proposed method.

4.2. Quasi-Isotropic Laminates

Fig.4.5 through 4.8 demonstrate the effect of varying 90° ply group thickness and laminate

order on matrix cracking in quasi-isotropic laminates. In graphs, by a dot line means occurrence of delamination, and indicates the onset of A.E.

Fig. 4.5 Stress-Strain and 90 ° Ply Group's Crack Density of $[45_1/-45_1/0_1/90_1]_s$

Fig.4.5 shows results of $[45_1/-45_1/0_1/90_1]_s$. The 90 ° ply group thickness is in the region of point A in Fig.1.2. Ply group thickness is so thin that stress criterion is satisfied former, and combined failure criterion becomes energy criterion. Although the matrix cracking assumes to be controlled by energy criterion, experimental behavior of crack initiation looks like to be close to calculated value on stress criterion. The discrepancy assumes to be the results of the free edge stress. Delamination occurs at 8500 μ . After delamination, stress does not transfer in 90 ° layer, and transverse crack growth is restrained. Delamination and free edge stress are not considered in this damage prediction method.

Fig. 4.6 Stress-Strain and 90 ° Ply Group's Crack Density of $[45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2]_s$

Fig.4.6 shows results of $[45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2]_s$. The 90 ° ply group thickness is in the region of point C in Fig.1.2. Ply group thickness is so thick that energy criterion is satisfied former, and combined failure criterion becomes stress criterion. Experimental value is predicted to be close to calculated value on stress criterion. Delamination occurs at 5500 μ . After

delamination, stress does not transfer in 90 ° layer, and transverse crack growth is restrained. There are only 90 ° ply group inside of 0 ° ply. No crack is observed in the other plies in experiment.

Fig. 4.7 Stress-Strain and 90 ° Ply Group's Crack Density of [45₁/0₁/-45₁/90₁]_s

Fig.4.7 shows results of [45₁/0₁/-45₁/90₁]_s. The 90 ° ply group thickness is in the region of point A in Fig.1.2. Ply group thickness is so thin that stress criterion is satisfied former, and combined failure criterion becomes energy criterion. Although the matrix cracking assumes to be controlled by energy criterion, experimental behavior of crack initiation looks like to be close to calculated value on stress criterion. The discrepancy assumes to be the results of the free edge stress. Delamination occurs at 8500 μ . After delamination, stress does not transfer in 90 ° layer, and transverse crack growth is restrained.

Fig. 4.8 -45 ° Ply's Crack Density of [45₁/0₁/-45₁/90₁]_s

Fig.4.8 shows -45 ° ply's crack density. Combined failure criterion is energy criterion in this ply. Matrix cracking initiates though there is no cracking in calculation. It is seemed that this is because of stress concentration by neighbor 90 ° ply's crack. Crack interaction between different plies is not considered in this damage prediction method.

5. CONCLUSION

In the present paper, we calculated crack growth and stiffness reduction based on energy criterion and stress criterion. The results of them are shown as follows.

In cross-ply laminates, exchanges of damage criteria with thickness of laminate are well explained by the present method.

In quasi-isotropic laminates, delamination effects transverse lamina crack growth. Delamination is not considered in the present method. There is discrepancy between calculated value and experimental value. Cracks in 90 ° ply give stress concentration to neighbor ply. It is easy for cracks to initiate and propagate in the neighbor ply because of stress concentration.

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